

ORIGINAL RESEARCH

The effect of physical fitness training on the performance of youth volleyball project players: the case of ana Lemo woreda, Hadiya zone, Ethiopia

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Abstract

The main objective of the study was to examine the effect of physical fitness training on the performance of youth volleyball project players: the case of ana lemo woreda, Hadiya zone. census sampling technique was used to select 24 players aged 15 to 16 years from ana Lemo woreda volleyball project players. The article focused on selected physical fitness variables. Those subjects under this study took part in experimental design pre and post-test on both tests from March 01/03/2021 to May 01/05/2021, 2 days per week for 3 months and 40 minutes precession. The physical fitness variables selected for the study were: cardiorespiratory endurance (1.6km run in min test), muscular endurance (sit-ups reps/60seconds), muscular strength (modified push-ups reps/30 seconds), power (standing long jump in meter), and agility (4x10 m shuttle run in seconds). Data were analyzed by using SPSS paired-samples t-test with a pair-wise comparison of means at a 95% confidence interval. The results indicated that there were significant improvements in performance on selected physical fitness variables due to the effect of physical fitness training with active rest (p < 0.05). This study confirmed that physical fitness training with active rest was significant to improve the physical fitness variables. The main finding of the study was trainee project players have discovered positive outcomes towards physical fitness variables. The study also illustrates that the health and fitness level of participants can be improved as a result of the physical fitness training program.

Keywords: Performance; Cardiorespiratory endurance; Muscular strength, Muscular endurance, power, and agility

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1.Introduction

The sport of volleyball of the project level comprises mainly of athletes of uncharacteristic size cardiovascular endurance, speed, agility, power, strength endurance level of fitness helped many athletes become strong and faster. Athletes spend tons of their time and energy trying to enhance their physical performance. strength and conditioning coaches have helped these athletes to achieve a high level of performance through resistance training. this training is used to help on improving the athlete's strength, power, flexibility, and speed. the improvement of all or one of these factors may help in enhancing the athlete's performance on his or her respective playing court. (Bangsbo,

2007) To cope with the physical requirements and to maintain technical standards throughout a match, the players must have a high level of fitness. playing suits frequently allows to hold the health degree of the player, however extra health It is necessary to obtain education. Volleyball instruction must be tailored to the sport, with a focus on executing the workout with a ball and separate physical education without the ball. The use of the ball during training ensures that the muscles used in volleyball are specifically trained, and it all checks the players' motivation. 2007 (Bangsbo) The observing athlete may also provide statistics on the players' physical characteristics to the educators. These figures can be used to forecast whether or not an athlete gamble. These figures could provide information to the coach about the players' physical condition. The data can then be